

INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-CREATIVE COMPETENCE ON THE EXAMPLE OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of social-creative competence development in future pedagogues, cognitive-methodical system of social-creative competence development and development of social activity skills and creative competence in future pedagogues in the conditions of reforms are studied. Also, the integrative methodology of development of socio-creative competence was analyzed on the example of Pedagogical sciences.

Key words: pedagogic, social-creative, competence, cognitive-methodical, social activity, skill, qualification, competence, integrative approach, development, pedagogical model, reproductive, functional.

INTRODUCTION. The requirements for the training of graduates of higher education institutions are specified in the State Educational Standards of Higher Education and Bachelor's Degrees and Master's Specialties. according to the "International Standard Classification of Education" introduced by the 6th qualification level.

The procedure for developing and implementing curricula is defined in the State Educational Standard of Higher Education, according to which the main goal of the bachelor's curriculum is to meet the requirements of the bachelor's qualifications in the state educational standards and qualification requirements. and for the preparation of competitive personnel, it consists of defining and regulating the educational subjects of certain undergraduate educational fields, their volume, types of training, the content, structure, duration and logical sequence of the educational process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of social activity among future pedagogues in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, Kh. Tojiboyeva, G. J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasovlar studied the development of social competence, while N. Azizkho'jayeva, A. Aripdzhanova, G. Ibragimova studied the aspects of teaching students to work creatively and developing different competencies in them. In the research works of N. Muslimov, O'. Tolipov, F. Exsonova, the problems of creative education were studied by M. Kadirova, Sh. Pozilova, A. Khalikov, Sh. Sharipov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. 60110100 - "Creative pedagogy" is located in the block of specialized subjects of the model curriculum awarding a bachelor academic degree in the field of pedagogy. " and "Social pedagogy" are the main pedagogical subjects in the development of socio-creative competencies of future pedagogues for our research work.

The goal of teaching "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" is to teach undergraduate students about the historical development of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy", development trends, the use of innovative methods of education, using the innovations of the world and world pedagogy. as a result of the implementation of advanced and modern information and communication technologies, preparation for implementation and formation of pedagogical culture, to develop their qualities such as independent creative work, meaningful activity, use of unusual methods in the performance of a task in their educational and future professional activities is to achieve, and in the process of studying science, the skills of a creative approach to any activity are improved.

As defined in the general requirements for the composition of professors and teachers of undergraduate education, in the implementation of the bachelor's curriculum and curriculum, basic information, knowledge, skills and experience in the subject being taught Qualified teachers, candidates of science, doctor of philosophy, associate professors, doctor of science, professors, persons with scientific, pedagogical and scientific titles, as well as highly qualified experts and practitioners with experience should be involved. , in addition to this, it is necessary for the professor-teacher of the higher education institution to move towards professional professionalism along with the acquisition of pedagogical competencies.

In general, in order for a pedagogue to develop social-creative competence in his students, first of all, it is necessary to have high skills, great knowledge, high moral virtue, in other words, social qualities and professional competence qualities. . A pedagogue is such a person that he should continuously work on himself, develop his socio-pedagogical characteristics and knowledge, be able to independently solve all problems in his professional activity, strive to perfect his social-creative qualities, and be innovative in every teaching process. Today's society needs such creative professors and teachers for the education of young people and the development of social and creative competencies in them. Because there are innovations and positive changes in every field, and as this is beneficial for society, the fact that every day, every lesson is full of unusual and

unexpected changes for the educational process will enliven the student's activity and education. contributes to its quality and productivity.

Today, professors and teachers in the world's most advanced higher education institutions use the "design thinking" approach to teach students, develop creative thinking skills, and create a new mind in them. The design thinking approach is a strategy to focus on the needs and wants of students, the learning process, and positively solve the problems that arise in this process in an innovative way. This helps the pedagogue to create a number of opportunities, such as conducting practical experiments in the educational process, gathering real feedback from students, and redesigning the educational process with the help of innovative solutions.

In many situations of the educational process, the activity of the pedagogue and the student is satisfied with the naturally repeated actions and thinking based on widespread knowledge. Design thinking, on the other hand, is based on the development of new ways of thinking that do not adhere to widely promoted methods, from a non-uniform solution to a problem. In this sense, at a time when the content of higher education is being raised to a new level in terms of quality in the process of the digital environment, it is necessary for students to think about their personal creative views, ideas, world changes within the framework of their social qualities and creative competence qualities. and the training of personnel who will respond with their actions and contribute to the sustainable improvement of social spheres and economic sectors is an urgent issue.

For this, it is necessary for each professor-teacher to learn and master advanced creative methods based on his personal program. It is required to continuously improve their skills through foreign experiences, electronic textbooks, manuals, and Internet news. Efforts to eliminate the shortcomings in the field of education today, the adoption of international standards and regulations, and the integration of educational and professional competencies based on world standards with national educational and professional competencies contribute to the integration of the new Uzbekistan into the international educational community. and serves to increase the quality of training of qualified personnel.

As the whole society is working to achieve this goal, the task of professors and teachers of higher education institutions is to help students to constantly search for themselves for their current and future activities, to develop themselves, to try to acquire the knowledge required by the times, to provide

the wealth of our nation. to be able to determine the direction of advanced ideas that determine the future of the country and nation on the basis of spiritual and cultural heritage and values, and to be able to realize the main task of applying this in practical processes, and to be able to develop social and creative qualities in students is important.

The wide-scale reforms implemented in new Uzbekistan and their results, news and developments, attention to students and young people and all the conditions created in them, the growth of modern intellectual potential, the changing state, society and individual needs, taking into account the demands of the modern times, which are updated and developed depending on the development of tomorrow, within the scope of today's possibilities of developing the social-creative competences of the students of the "Pedagogy" field of education in the process of preparing them for practical-pedagogical activities necessary social order can be cited.

In the process of preparing future pedagogues for practical-pedagogical activities, acquiring professional competence, it is important to take into account the above-mentioned requirements as existing opportunities to regularly develop social-creative competence in them.

The existing possibilities of developing socio-creative competence in future pedagogues also represent the existing system of requirements in the direction of the need to develop these qualities in them. The mentioned existing possibilities are to ensure consistency and continuity in the development of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues, to establish standards and requirements for the qualifications of students and graduates, to implement an objective system of evaluating the quality of education and personnel training, to ensure the beneficial integration of education, science and production in order to train personnel in a purposeful and qualitative manner, to ensure consistency in the content of education, interdependence of education and training, types of continuous education and personnel training determines.

In order to ensure systematic development of socio-creative competence of future pedagogues, the topics specified in the program on the integration of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" subjects taught to them should be adapted to norms, requirements, norms, universal values, national and world standards. appropriate and paying attention to the individuality of each student, it is considered important to connect with concepts in the directions of social activity, creativity, competence, their essence, importance and necessity. This, in

turn, determines the need to improve the model of the process of developing socio-creative competence in future pedagogues.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, social-creative competencies are the main factor in the formation and development of a person, and by realizing the essence of this concept and embodying this quality, students can achieve creative growth in their current and future activities, purposefully and successfully. to create innovations, as a result of which creative reform of one's lifestyle and society is achieved.

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